

FEASIBLE MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF STRUCTURAL BATTERY ELECTRODES

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ABSTRACT

Structural batteries (SBs) are a potential solution to reduce weight in electric vehicles and thus to improve their system efficiencies. A structural battery is based on the concept of a traditional carbon fiber reinforced composite material which possesses high structural performance at low weight. The key benefit compared to a conventional composite material is that a SB material simultaneously functions as lithium-ion (Li-ion) battery. Therefore, a multifunctional lightweight material is obtained that can store energy and it can be used directly in structural applications. One big field of application is thus the transport sector where monofunctional structures can be replaced with multifunctional SBs. However, this technology is still in its early development stage. In order to integrate it into an application several challenges remain to be solved; e.g. the development of a feasible composite manufacturing process that ensures the multifunctional performance of an SB. A robust and simple process method suitable for the fabrication of multiple layers of full-cell structural batteries is demonstrated. This process maintains the desired multifunctional properties of the multifunctional matrix material, which is essential for its performance. Furthermore, the processing technique is also evaluated with respect to the mechanical and electrochemical performance of a UD-lamina negative half-cell.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electrification of vehicles provides large potential to reduce emissions from transportation. Weight reduction and thus an increase in energy efficiency is a potential route towards the implementation of electric vehicles on a large scale. The concept of structural batteries providing massless energy is promising to reduce significant amounts of weight and was rated among the top 10 research breakthroughs in Physics World 2018 [1].

Structural batteries are lightweight composite materials with high structural performance and an energy storage function as a Li-ion battery. Thus, parasitic structures in electric vehicles can be replaced by multifunctional composite structures (i.e. structural batteries) since they allow for weight savings on a systems level [2]. A central aspect in this multifunctional composite is that each of the embedded constituents are multifunctional.

Similar to a conventional battery, a structural battery is composed of two electrodes, a separator and an electrolyte matrix (see figure 1).

Figure 1 Structural battery as part of the car body.

Structural batteries make use of carbon fibers that function as electrodes and structural reinforcement at the same time. The negative electrode is composed of commercially available carbon fibers since the structure can intercalate Li-ions. The positive electrode is made of carbon fibers coated with electrochemically active material (LiFePO_4). The negative and the positive electrodes are separated by a separator that prevents electrical short-circuiting. The carbon fibers and the separator are embedded in a structural battery electrolyte (SBE) matrix that enables conduction of Li-ions and structural load transfer simultaneously.

One challenge is for the SBE to provide sufficient ionic conductivity and load transfer at the same time since these are competing properties. Commercially used liquid electrolytes do not have any structural performance while solid polymer electrolytes lack in sufficient ionic conductivity.

Therefore, a bi-continuous SBE has been developed for structural batteries [3]. The SBE is made of a percolating network of a solid and a liquid on the submicron scale. The solid phase delivers structural integrity while the liquid ensures good ionic conductivity. The bi-continuous SBE and a UD-lamina structural battery half-cell have previously been fabricated by UV-initiated polymerization induced phase separation [3]. However, with this technique it is not possible to make a full-cell structural battery due to insufficient UV-light penetration through thick composites.

In this work, a well-known composite processing technique is presented to make multifunctional SBs. This processing technique is scalable and ensures the desired multifunctional performance. Furthermore, the processing technique is also evaluated with respect to the mechanical and electrochemical performance of a unidirectional-lamina negative half-cell. The cycling performance of structural electrodes containing different types of CFs and their effect on multifunctional properties is included as well.

Figure 2: Simple manufacturing method for a structural battery electrode.

2 TECHNIQUES AND PROCEDURE

2.1 Resin Preparation

The resin (i.e. polymer electrolyte) was prepared in an argon filled glovebox and dry conditions (<1 ppm H₂O, <1 ppm O₂) according to the recipe as described by Schneider et al. [4]. A stock solution of liquid organic electrolyte was prepared and used for all samples. The liquid electrolyte was an ethylene carbonate (99%, anhydrous) (EC) and Dimethyl methylphosphonate (97%) (DMMP) (50:50 wt%) based mixture, with a 1M concentration of lithium trifluoromethanesulfonate (LiTFS) (96%). The structural battery electrolyte (SBE) solution was obtained by mixing the monomer SR348L (bisphenol A ethoxylate dimethacrylate, M_n: 540 g mol⁻¹) with liquid electrolyte (39wt% of the total weight) and the heat initiator 2,2'-Azobis(2-methylpropionitrile) (AIBN) (1wt% of the monomer weight). The container of the solution was sealed with a septum in the glovebox since the manufacturing is made outside the glovebox. This step was done in order to prevent the resin to react with moisture and air.

2.2 Structural Electrode Manufacturing

Structural CF electrodes were prepared using vacuum infusion and heat curing. Then, half-cells were made and sealed in a pouch cell. CFs of the following types were used: T800S (12k) from Toray provided as 10 mm spread tows from Oxeon AB with a linear weight of the fibers of 0.52 g m⁻¹ and T800H (6k) from Toray hand-spread to approximately 10 mm with a linear weight of 0.23 g m⁻¹. The fibers were taped onto a glass plate (150 x 70 mm). Copper foil current collectors were attached to the spread CFs with Electrolube silver conductive paint. The CFs were covered with firstly a perforated polyethylene film (release film), secondly breather fabric (distribution medium of coarse polyester felt cloth) and it was then sealed using a vacuum bag and rubber vacuum tape. Before vacuum infusion,

the samples were dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C for 12 h in order to remove residual moisture. The SBE resin was prepared in the glovebox in a dry argon atmosphere (<1 ppm H₂O, <1 ppm O₂) as described in the section resin preparation. The vacuum infusion of the prepared glass plate with CFs was executed outside the glove box. Directly after infusion, the structural electrodes were heat cured in a preheated oven at 80 or 90 °C for 75 and 45 minutes, respectively.

2.3 Structural Battery Half-Cell Preparation

After curing, a two-electrode pouch cell (70 x 70 mm) was assembled in dry argon atmosphere (<1 ppm H₂O, <1 ppm O₂) with the sequence: a cured structural electrode with copper current collector (i.e. CF lamina) (10 x 31 mm) as working electrode, a Whatman glass-microfiber filter as a separator and lithium metal foil as counter electrode with a nickel current collector. The separator film was soaked with small amounts (around 200 µl) of additional liquid electrolyte to ensure ionic conduction. The entire assembly was vacuum-sealed in a pouch cell.

2.4 Testing of a Half-Cell and Structural Electrode

In order to estimate the electrochemical performance of the structural electrodes, the pouch cells were galvanostatically cycled between 0.02 V and 1.5 V vs. Li/Li⁺ at 18.6 mA g⁻¹ for 10 cycles at ambient temperature. The electrode capacities were calculated based on a linear weight of the CFs (0.52 g m⁻¹).

The mechanical integrity of the structural electrodes was estimated by evaluating the elastic modulus of the composite electrode in the transverse direction using a three-point bending set-up as previously done by Johansson et al. [2]. The same experimental procedure was applied: the structural electrodes were glued to a PET substrate and the bending stiffness of the entire assembly was determined. Then, the transverse modulus was back-calculated from the samples' bending stiffness using standard laminate theory [5].

2.5 Scanning Electron Microscopy

SEM was used to investigate the microstructure of SBEs, by looking at the cross-sections of cured SBE films. For the SEM analysis a Hitachi S-4800 equipped with a cold field-emission electron source was used. Before analysis, the samples were immersed in water for 24 h to extract the liquid electrolyte (LiTFS, EC and DMMP). The samples were then dried in a vacuum oven overnight at 60 °C. The samples were then cooled with liquid nitrogen and fractured. The samples were mounted into a split mold and the fractured cross-section was coated with Pt/Pd using an Agar HR sputter coater. A sputtered layer thickness of 3 nm was chosen for sufficient conductivity of the sample.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural Battery Electrolyte Properties

Investigations of the SBE matrix without CFs indicated that a porous SBE matrix on the submicron scale with desired properties is also obtained when using heat curing. The chemical conversion of the polymer matrix is higher in heat cured systems compared to UV- cured systems. A conversion around 95% was obtained for systems cured at 80 °C for 75 min or 90 °C for 45 min, while the UV cured SBE samples showed a conversion around 85%. The higher conversion leads to a better thermomechanical performance and it can be particularly beneficial for the use in battery applications. It has also been shown that the curing temperature 70 - 90°C does not have a large effect on the SBE morphology. The ionic conductivity also remains at the same level when compared to the UV cured matrix of about 2x10⁻⁴ mS cm⁻¹, which strengthens the fact that the obtained system is robust and suitable for battery applications. As a result, a curing temperature between 80 – 90 °C is suitable for processing of the structural electrodes. [4]

3.1 Morphology of Structural Electrodes

The morphology of the matrix and fracture interface of T800S carbon fiber and SBE matrix is shown in figure 3. The images show virgin compared to electrochemically cycled structural electrodes. All images indicate that the CFs were embedded into an electrolyte matrix with a porosity on the submicron scale. In addition, the surface of uncycled carbon fibers appears smoother compared to uncycled fibers and should be investigated further.

Figure 3: SEM images of structural electrodes including T800S CFs cycled and virgin. Carbon fiber with polymer matrix residue: cycled at 7k (a), virgin at 7k (b); carbon fiber imprint: cycled at 2.5k (c), virgin at 4.5k (d). The liquid electrolyte has been extracted beforehand in all samples.

3.2 Multifunctional Performance of Structural Electrodes

The electrochemical cycling of a structural electrode in a battery half-cell show that heat curing is a feasible process to make SBs since the multifunctional properties can be maintained. The manufacturing process of the structural electrode is also practically feasible for composite manufacturing. The uncured SBE matrix is a low viscosity resin and thus good wetting of CFs is possible and benefits the formation of a CF-SBE structural interface. The transverse modulus of the cycled UD laminae electrode of T800S fibers was estimated to 1.3 +/- 0.1 GPa which is higher compared to the modulus of around 530 MPa at 25 °C measured with dynamic mechanical analysis on the SBE film without carbon fibers [4]. This is an indication that this electrode also shows structural performance. In previous study it was shown that electrochemical cycling does influence the structural performance of these electrodes [2].

However, in this multifunctional material, the interface should also possess multiple functions and also allow for the transport of Li-ions. The electrochemical functioning of the structural electrodes is confirmed by the charging/ discharging performance of two different types of carbon fibers. Figure 4 and 5 show the potential profiles for cycle 1, 2 and 10 for a structural electrode with T800H fibers and a structural electrode with T800S fibers, respectively. The potential profiles of the T800H fiber are comparable with the potential profiles of UV cured structural electrodes obtained in previous work [3] where the same type of fiber was used. This supports the fact that the change in processing method does not affect the electrochemical performance. The decrease in capacity after the first cycle (figure 4 and 5) for both fibers is a common feature in Li-ion batteries and is governed by SEI layer formation and irreversibly trapped lithium in the carbon fibers [6,7]. Figure 6 illustrates the capacity vs. cycle number for 10 cycles at current density of 18.6 mA g^{-1} for a structural electrode with T800S fibers and a structural electrode with T800H. Both electrodes show a stable discharge/ charge behavior over 10 cycles. Both fiber types show electrochemical performance when cycling versus lithium in a half-cell setup. However, the T800H fibers show superior electrochemical performance compared to T800S. Specifically, the T800H fiber reaches a reversible capacity of around 197 mAh g^{-1} while the T800S fiber reaches a capacity of around 114 mAh g^{-1} at a current density of 18.6 mA g^{-1} . Furthermore, the overpotentials are lower in the T800H fiber (compare figure 4 and 5). The fiber types are the same, but tow size and sizing differs between the T800H and T800S. The lower electrochemical performance of T800S could be an effect the larger tow size. This leads an electrode thickness of an electrode thickness of $44 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ for T800H [2] and $90 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ for T800S fibers [4]. Thicker electrodes can limit the mass transfer of Li-ions. Another difference in these carbon fibers is that the sizing is different. This can make a difference in compatibility with the SBE used. If the matrix is more compatible with the sizing; it can favor the formation of a structural interface between the solid part of the matrix and the fibers; while electrochemical properties can suffer due to less access of the liquid electrolyte to the fibers. Generally speaking, the results show that there is a lot of potential for performance optimization of these systems when applying slight variations in fiber characteristics. This could be a potential route to increase performance of the negative electrode and thus bring SBs closer to an actual application.

To summarize, the main benefits of these structural electrodes are that they are lightweight materials that can offer electrochemical and mechanical performance simultaneously. It was found that heat curing is an adequate process to produce multifunctional electrodes. Furthermore, the characteristics of the fibers allow for system optimization, which will be done in future studies along with the development of a positive electrode and the assembly of a full cell SB with adequate performance.

Figure 4: Potential profiles for the 1st, 2nd and 10th cycle of a T800H-SBE composite half-cell, charged and discharged at a current density of 18.6 mA g^{-1} and thermally cured at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 45 min.

Figure 5: Potential profiles for the 1st, 2nd and 10th cycle of a T800H-SBE composite half-cell, charged and discharged at a current density of 18.6 mA g^{-1} and thermally cured at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 75 min.

Figure 6: Capacity vs cycle number two CF-SBE half-cell T800H (green) thermally cured at 90°C for 45 min and T800S (blue) 80 °C for 75 min. A current density of 18.6 mA g⁻¹ was applied over 10 cycles.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Vacuum infusion in combination with heat curing was presented as a suitable manufacturing technique to manufacture multilayer stacks of structural batteries. The performance analysis of the structural electrode confirmed that multifunctional performance is maintained, and conversions can be increased with heat curing. Suitable curing conditions were found to be between 80 °C or 90 °C for 75 or 45 minutes, respectively. The data also shows that thermal curing does not decrease the electrochemical performance compared to the UV-cured system of the same composition. Furthermore, the use of adequate fibers with specific characteristics provides a possibility for performance optimization.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Demming, 2018, Breakthrough of the Year: Anna Demming's shortlist, accessed 20.6.2019, (available at: <https://physicsworld.com/a/2018-breakthrough-of-the-year-anna-demmings-shortlist/>).
- [2] W. Johansson, N. Ihrner, D. Zenkert, M. Johansson, D. Carlstedt, L. E. Asp, F. Sieland, Multifunctional performance of a carbon fiber UD lamina electrode for structural batteries, *Composite Science and Technology*, **168**, 2018, pp. 81–87. (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.08.044](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.08.044)).
- [3] N. Ihrner, W. Johansson, F. Sieland, D. Zenkert, M. Johansson, Structural lithium ion battery electrolytes via reaction induced phase-separation, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*.

The Royal Society of Chemistry, **5** (48), 2017, pp. 25652–25659. (doi: [10.1039/C7TA04684G](https://doi.org/10.1039/C7TA04684G)).

- [4] L. M. Schneider, N. Ihrner, D. Zenkert, M. Johansson, Bicontinuous electrolytes via thermally initiated polymerization for structural lithium ion batteries, *ACS Applied Energy Materials*. American Chemical Society, (doi: [10.1021/acsaem.9b00563](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.9b00563)).
- [5] D. Agarwal, L. J. Broutman and K. Chandrashekhara, *Analysis and performance of fiber composites*, edition 4, John Wiley & Sons, 2017.
- [6] E. Peled, The electrochemical behavior of alkali and alkaline earth metals in nonaqueous battery systems - the solid electrolyte interphase model, *Journal of Electrochemical Society*, **126** (12), 1979, pp. 2047– 2051, (doi: [10.1149/1.2128859](https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2128859)).
- [7] Aurbach, B. Markovsky, M. D. Levi, E. Levi, A. Schechter, M. Moshkovich, Y. Cohen, New insights into the interactions between electrode materials and electrolyte solutions for advanced nonaqueous batteries, *Journal of Power Sources*, **81**, 1999, pp. 95–111 (doi: [10.1016/S0378-7753\(99\)00187-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(99)00187-1)).